

A Neural Net Model to Represent Negotiators' Heuristics

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Abstract

This paper demonstrates the use of neural networks to represent the complex thought process of the negotiators. Using the pattern matching concept, the paper presents an innovative way to capture the heuristics of the decision makers involved in a bilateral negotiation. A significant advantage of using our representation scheme is the relative ease of recognition of the relations inherent within a negotiation problem.

Introduction

Negotiation Support Systems (NSS) are designed to assist negotiators in reaching mutually satisfactory decisions by providing a means of communication and through factual analysis of available information (e.g., Bui, 1991). To be effective, a NSS should support each of the individual users so that their needs can be taken into consideration in the analysis of alternatives and solutions (e.g., Bui, 1992). Most of the NSS reported in the literature adopt a prescriptive approach in that they provide users with analytical models (e.g., multi-attribute utility theory, Nash solution, and Pareto optimization) to search for group solutions. From that perspective, little effort is made to capture the true behavior of the negotiator that may contain irrational elements. With some exception, Kersten and Szapiro (1986) attempt to provide a generalized approach to modeling negotiations. They assume that pressure constitute a primary driver in decision making. Such a modeling approach, although useful in understanding the causal effect of pressure on bargaining outcome, still suffers from providing a wholistic description of the complex thought process of the negotiator. This paper attempts to use the pattern matching concept in neural network to describe that thought process. This paper is not intended to be a comprehensive

analysis of negotiation, nor is it a survey of the broad spectrum of neural paradigms. Rather, it seeks to use a neural network as a pattern matching scheme to represent the negotiator's mental model.

Modeling Negotiation Using Neural Networks

Neural networks provide an unique means of seeking a solution to a problem Jorgensen and Matheus (1986). Successful neural network applications have the following general characterizations (e.g., Bailey, 1990):

- Conventional computer technology is inadequate
- Problem requires qualitative or complex quantitative reasoning
- Data is readily available but multivariate, noisy or error prone
- Solution is derived from highly interdependent parameters which have no precise quantification
- Algorithmic solution is unknown, difficult or expensive

We contend that negotiation problems share the same characterizations. In this paper, we demonstrate that the thought process of the negotiator — i.e., his/her preferences, perception of the problems, constraints and decision rules — can be represented in neural networks. Each network is capable of evaluating the available options which the negotiator will consider in a manner consistent with his preferences. These networks do not provide analytical models of how a negotiator *should* make a decision. They provide models of how the negotiator *will* make a decision incorporating any possible irrationalities the negotiator may possess.

The neural networks presented in this paper possess *a priori* information about how a negotiator will evaluate a given negotiation situation. Each

neural element will represent an idea the negotiator has about what is important to making a decision. The collective activation of a set of these elements will simulate the process a negotiator would do in evaluating the negotiation situation according to what he perceived to be important. In neural network terminology, the neural elements are activated by matching a pattern of activity input to the network to a known pattern of activity among the elements which represent *a priori* information about the problem to be solved.

A Neural Model of the Negotiator's Thought Process: The Case of a Bicycle Buyer

In this section, we use an example to describe the process of building a neural network to represent the thought processes of a negotiator. Due to the complexity of the neural network structure, this paper considers only a bilateral setting with two agents involving only one bargaining issue. A neural solution to a single issue negotiation problem will act as a stepping stone in the development of a more comprehensive neural solution to negotiation.

Problem Definition

The network described here will simulate the decision making processes of a buyer attempting to purchase a bicycle. We assume a "soft" negotiation environment, that is, both parties attempt to cooperate to find a mutually beneficial agreement. The buyer will attempt to purchase the bicycle for the lowest amount possible but he will readily concede some amount of money to maintain a good relationship with the seller. He establishes the following five strategies:

1. If there is no current buyer offer, offer \$100.
2. If both buyer and seller offer same amount, accept that amount.
3. If the buyer and seller differ by \$10, accept the seller's price.
4. If the buyer and seller differ by more than \$10, the buyer will concede \$20 only if he is currently offering \$100 or \$110.
5. Once the buyer offers \$120, only \$10 will be given up at a time until agreement is reached.

It is important to note here that it is not required

to impose *rationality* behind these strategies. It is crucial, however, that strategies are well formulated enough so that they can be represented in the network.

Network Representation

The ability to simulate the logical decision making processes of a negotiator depends on how well the network capture all elements of the negotiation process. Limited to the buyer's perspective, this network will contain four representations:

1. The buyer's current offer
2. The seller's current offer
3. A comparison of the offers
4. The buyer's response to the seller's offer

Based on these representations, a neural network acts as a memory device containing negotiation elements which can be connected together to create a picture of the possible states of the negotiation (Caudill, 1989, 1991). Whenever a negotiation condition changes (e.g., a seller's new offer), a "new" picture of the environment will be generated.

Paradigm Selection

The engine chosen for this model is the Constraint Satisfaction (CS) network provided by Rumelhart and McClelland (1988). CS networks work on the principle that each node is a hypothesis, and connections between nodes are constraints between hypotheses. The importance of the constraint may be coded into the weight of the connection. An important constraint would have a large value while those not so important would have lessor values.

Rumelhart and McClelland (1988) view external input as evidence to a hypothesis. If there is prior evidence that a hypothesis may be true or false, that evidence can be represented by assigning a bias term ($bias_i$) to node i . The bias will activate (positive) or deactivate (negative) a node in the absence of other evidence.

The connection weight, w_{ij} , is the strength of the connection to node i from node j . In the CS network the connections are symmetric, (i.e., $w_{ij} = w_{ji}$), and a node may not connect with itself (i.e., $w_{ii} = 0$).

The state of activation of node i at time t is $a_i(t)$. The state of activation is updated according to the following equations:

$$a_i(t+1) = a_i(t) + net_i(1-a_i(t))$$

if $net_i > 0$

and

$$a_i(t+1) = a_i(t) + net_i a_i(t)$$

if $net_i < 0$

The net input to a node (net_i) is determined according to the following equation:

$$net_i = istr(\sum_j w_{ij} a_j + bias_i) + estr(input_i)$$

The *istr* term is a scaling term which affects the network generated inputs to a node. The *estr* term is a scaling factor which affects the external input to a node.

Nodes are randomly updated asynchronously within the network. This update technique developed by Hopfield has the advantage of maintaining better stability by reducing oscillations between states, than synchronous update where all units are updated at the same instant (Rumelhart and McClelland, 1986).

Rumelhart and McClelland use the term "goodness of fit" to describe how well a CS network satisfies constraints. This measure depends on three factors: (i) the extent to which each unit satisfies the constraints imposed on it by other units; (ii) the a priori strength of the hypothesis is captured by adding the bias to the goodness measure; and (iii) the goodness of fit for a hypothesis when direct evidence is available is given by the product of the input value times the activation value of the unit.

The equation below is used to measure the goodness of a single node within a network.

$$goodness_i = \sum_j w_{ij} a_j + input_i + bias_i a_i$$

The overall goodness of the network can be measured with:

$$goodness = \sum_{ij} w_{ij} a_j + \sum_i input_i + \sum_i bias_i a_i$$

During processing, the network will maximize its

goodness of fit measure. External inputs will provide a stimulus to a set of nodes. The remaining nodes will or will not be activated depending on how they affect the overall goodness measure.

Network Configuration

As discussed above, the buyer's strategies have to be represented in the network. In addition to the four strategies identified by the buyer (see Problem Definition), a fifth representation is needed to account for a possible situation in which the buyer may not have made an offer, i.e., the absence of a buyer offer.

Each of the representations will be broken into a set of nodes (hypotheses) and connections (constraints) corresponding to the discrete values possible during the negotiation. Each node will have a continuous activation range from zero to one. We assume that the buyer would prefer to pay only \$100 but will pay \$150 if necessary. The buyer knows that the seller will ask a maximum of \$150 and may consider \$100 acceptable. Therefore, the buyer's current offer and the seller's current offer may be broken into twelve individual nodes, six per person (indicated by black dots shown in Figure 1).

Figure 1. Buyer and Seller input representations

The buyer will only be concerned with the difference between his current offer and the seller's current offer for making a decision as to what next to offer. To represent the difference in offers, it is necessary to have twenty one buyer-seller representations. Six of them are necessary for a buyer offer of \$100: (\$100,\$100), (\$100,\$110), (\$100,\$120), (\$100,\$130), (\$100,\$140), (\$100,\$150). Following the same line of representation, five representations are necessary for a \$110 buyer offer; (\$110,\$110), (\$110,\$120), (\$110,\$130), (\$110,\$140),

(\$110,\$150). Etc. Each combination of buyer/seller/ comparison node is a single representation (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Individual comparison representations

Furthermore, since the buyer is concerned with the exact difference in offers when a seller's offer is \$20 greater than the buyer's offer, the number of comparison nodes may be reduced to fifteen. Three comparison nodes are necessary for each buyer offer less than \$140 (agree, disagree by \$10, disagree by \$20 or more). Two comparison nodes are necessary for the \$140 buyer offer (agree, disagree by \$10). The \$150 offer requires only one comparison node (agreement). Figure 3 shows how the number of comparison nodes would be reduced. "A" represents agreement, "D" represents disagreement by \$10, "D+" represents disagreement by two or more dollars. There are still twenty one representations or "pictures". The D+ nodes act as concentration points for a number of representations. For example, the \$100 D+ node completes four possible representations (\$100,\$120), (\$100,\$130), (\$100,\$140) and (\$100,\$150). Conceptually, the buyer has categorized the environment into fifteen different views or pictures. After the initial offers are established, the buyer will increase an offer based on the difference between his and the seller's offer. If there is no difference, the buyer will accept that offer (strategy 2). If the seller asks a \$10 more than the buyer's current offer, the buyer will meet the seller's price (strategy 3). If the buyer is offering \$100 or \$110 and the seller is asking \$20 or more than the buyer is offering, the buyer will

increase the offer by \$20 (strategy 4).

After the buyer has reached the \$120 point, only a \$10 will be conceded (strategy 5). Figure 4 shows the relations between the comparison nodes and the desired responses. There are fifteen different views of the environment but only six different actions which the buyer may take on the environment. Since there are only six possible actions or response values (\$100 - \$150), the responses may be merged together as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 3. Individual action responses

Figure 4. Combined action responses

A special case occurs when the buyer may not have made an offer, preferring to let the seller begin negotiation. A representation of the absence of a buyer offer is necessary. The no offer node in combination with all of the buyer input nodes will create the representation of the absence of a buyer

offer. The desired action in the absence of a current buyer offer is for the buyer to offer \$100 (strategy 1). If any of the buyer nodes are active, the no offer node must be inactive (Figure 6).

Figure 5. No offer representations

Since inputs from both buyer and seller are necessary to activate a comparison node, the connection weight should be set so that activation of a single input node does not activate a comparison node. All weights are symmetrical in a CS network. If a single input node were allowed to activate a comparison node a comparison node would be able to activate an input node, the entire set of nodes would soon become active. There is no automatic decay mechanism in the CS paradigm. When a node becomes active, it will stay active unless it is specifically instructed to do otherwise.

There are two tools available to control activation. Inhibition connections and negative bias. Inhibition connections could be established between each of the nodes in each set (ie. each buyer node inhibits all of the other buyer nodes, each comparison node inhibits all other comparison nodes, etc). A combination of negative bias and connection weight could also be used. Negative bias ensures that a node remains inactive until the weighted activation ($\sum wa$) becomes greater than the negative bias.

For this model negative bias will be used. It is simpler to modify than inhibition connections. Each

of the input and comparison nodes will be assigned a bias of -0.7 . The connection weight between the inputs and the comparison nodes will be $+0.5$. Between the comparison and response nodes the connection weight will be $+0.1$. No bias is necessary for the response nodes. The bias value of -0.7 ensures that an input node will not be erroneously activated by a single active comparison node which is connected to it and that a comparison node will not be activated by a single active input node.

The equation below shows how the activation of the \$100 D+ node will be computed (see constraint satisfaction description). The buyer and seller are limited to a single offer at a time. When that offer is made, the activation level of the input nodes will be "clamped" to 1.0.

$$\sum_0^{12} 0.5a_{input} = 0.5a_{B1} + 0.5a_{S3} + 0.5a_{S4} + 0.5a_{S5} + 0.5a_{S6} + 0.1a_r$$

$$net_{D+} = \sum_0^{12} 0.5a_{input} + (-0.7)$$

when $net_{D+} > 0$ then

$$a_{D+}(t+1) = a_{D+}(t) + net_{D+}(1 - a_{D+}(t))$$

else when $net_{D+} < 0$

$$a_{D+}(t+1) = a_{D+}(t) + net_{D+}a_{D+}(t)$$

In this example, we assume that the current offers are (\$100,\$120) and time $t=1$ for the comparison node. The \$100 D+ node will receive a net input of 0.3 ($1.0 + -0.7$). No other node will receive a net input greater than 0 due to the negative bias associated with it. The activation level of this D+ node (assuming that it was previously inactive) will become 0.3 ($0 + 0.3(1 - 0)$).

When this D+ node becomes fully active (1.0) it will not be able to activate any input node. The maximum net input to any other input node (except 1,3) is -0.2 ($0.5 + -0.7$).

When the D+ node becomes active, it will send an activation signal to the \$120 response node. The symmetrical connections then allow the \$120 response node to reinforce the \$100 D+ node. The same symmetrical connections also allow the \$120 response node to send an activation signal to the \$110 D comparison node. The \$110 D comparison node will receive activation signals from the seller \$120 offer node and the \$120 response node. This node will

receive a net input of -0.1 (0.5 + 0.1 + 0.7).

The *no offer* node is biased slightly on (+0.1). The connection weight between it and the buyer input nodes is strongly inhibitory (-1.0). The connection weight between it and the \$100 response node is positive (+0.1).

The completed model consists of a parallel architecture consisting of 34 nodes and 53 symmetric connections. Figure 6 shows the layout of the connections and nodes. For clarity, some of the connections from the *buyer* and *seller* input nodes to the feature nodes are not shown.

Figure 6. Network Architecture

The *buyer* and *seller* nodes act as binary nodes due to clamping. Each node represents a specific number of dollars each participant is currently offering. The *response* nodes respond with the new dollar amount which the buyer should offer to the seller. Each node corresponds to a specific dollar amount. The *response* nodes react to the activation of specific *comparison nodes*.

Negotiation Simulation with the Network

To trigger an offer when there is no current offer, the *no offer* node is biased (+0.1) to be active. It has a small weight (+0.1) connecting it to the first *response* node. The connection with the *buyer* nodes is negative (-1.0) which will effectively turn the node off if the buyer has a current offer.

If there is no current offer by the buyer, the

buyer nodes will be inactive. Figure 7 shows the connections and nodes involved with this state of activity. The empty nodes represent inactivity while the filled in nodes are active.

Figure 7. No Offer

The output screen is shown in Figure 8. Only the \$100 response offer on the far right is active. The level of activity of the no offer node is not displayed.

```

disp/ exam/ get/ save/ set/ clear cycle do input log
newstart quit reset run test

(buyer model)
recommended
bid price agree weakly strongly bid
0 b 0 one 0 a1 0 d1 0 d1+ 9 one
0 u 0 two 0 a2 0 d2 0 d2+ 0 two
0 y 0 three 0 a3 0 d3 0 d3+ 0 three
0 e 0 four 0 a4 0 d4 0 d4+ 0 four
0 r 0 five 0 a5 0 d5 0 five
0 0 six 0 a6 0 six

0 s 0 one
0 e 0 two
0 l 0 three
0 l 0 four
0 e 0 five
0 r 0 six

```

Figure 8. Buyer offers one dollar

When the buyer and seller differ by \$20 or more, the network will attempt to seek a quick compromise only if the buyer is offering \$100 or \$110. The 100D+ & 110D+ nodes and connections represent this idea. These nodes are biased (-0.7) to be inactive unless both the buyer and seller nodes which are connected with them are active. The connection strength between the D+ nodes and the buyer and seller nodes is +0.5 and the connection strength with the response node is +0.1. The connection strengths are the same for all input/feature and feature/response connections. Figure 9 shows the set of connections that supports this idea.

Figure 9. Seek quick agreement

In Figure 10, the 100D+ node detects that the buyer is offering \$100 and the seller is asking \$120 or more. This node and all of the active nodes connected to it, represent the schema in which the buyer is offering \$100 and the seller is asking \$120 or more and, the buyer should increase his bid by \$20. When the \$120 response node becomes active a complete schema is formed. The network has effectively filled in the missing piece of the schema by activating the \$120 response node.

The output screen for this state of activation is shown in Figure 10. The active nodes are underlined.

```

disp/ exam/ get/ save/ set/ clear cycle do input log
newstart quit reset run test

(buyer model)
recommended
bid price agree weakly strongly bid
* b 10 one 0 a1 0 d1 9 d1+ 0 one
0 u 0 two 0 a2 0 d2 0 d2+ 0 two
0 y 0 three 0 a3 0 d3 0 d3+ 7 three
0 e 0 four 0 a4 0 d4 0 d4+ 0 four
0 r 0 five 0 a5 0 d5 0 five
0 0 six 0 a6 0 six

0 s 0 one
0 e 0 two
0 l 0 three
0 l 0 four
* e 10 five
0 r 0 six
  
```

Figure 10. Seek quick agreement display

Figure 11 shows the state of the network after the buyer has increased the offer to \$120 and the seller has reduced the price to \$130. The active nodes are filled in. The output screen is shown in Figure 12. The active nodes are underlined. The buyer and seller agree to settle at \$130 (Figure 13).

Figure 11. Buyer and seller differ by one dollar

Figure 14 shows the screen display when both parties agree to \$130.

```

disp/ exam/ get/ save/ set/ clear cycle do input log
newstart quit reset run test
(buyer model)
recommended
bid price agree weakly strongly bid
0 b 0 one 0 a1 0 d1 0 d1+ 0 one
0 u 0 two 0 a2 0 d2 0 d2+ 0 two
* y 10 three 0 a3 9 d3 0 d3+ 0 three
0 e 0 four 0 a4 0 d4 0 d4+ 9 four
0 r 0 five 0 a5 0 d5 0 five
0 0 six 0 a6 0 six

0 s 0 one
0 e 0 two
0 l 0 three
* l 10 four
0 e 0 five
0 r 0 six

```

Figure 12. Buyer offers three and seller asks four dollars

```

disp/ exam/ get/ save/ set/ clear cycle do input log
newstart quit reset run test
(buyer model)
recommended
bid price agree weakly strongly bid
0 b 0 one 0 a1 0 d1 0 d1+ 0 one
0 u 0 two 0 a2 0 d2 0 d2+ 0 two
0 y 0 three 0 a3 0 d3 0 d3+ 0 three
* e 10 four 9 a4 0 d4 0 d4+ 9 four
0 r 0 five 0 a5 0 d5 0 five
0 0 six 0 a6 0 six

0 s 0 one
0 e 0 two
0 l 0 three
* l 10 four
0 e 0 five
0 r 0 six

```

Figure 15. Buyer and seller agree to four dollars

Figure 13. Buyer and seller agree

Figure 14. Concede only one dollar

To test the strategy of conceding a \$10 when the buyer offer is \$120 or more, the buyer offer will be set to \$120 and the seller offer will be set to \$140. Figure 18 shows this state of the network. The $120D+$ and $130D+$ nodes like the $100D+$ and $110D+$ nodes represent the idea that there is a \$20 or more difference between the buyer and seller. The difference between these pairs of nodes ($120D+$, $130D+$ and $100D+$, $110D+$) is that the buyer changes his strategy when currently offering \$120 or more. Rather than increasing by \$20, the buyer will now increase by only \$10. This is an attempt to encourage the seller to decrease the asking price by indicating reluctance to increase the bid.

Discussions

The neural network developed in this paper has demonstrated the ability to mimic some simple thought processes of a negotiator. We were able to model a bilateral negotiation from the point of view of the buyer; the seller being the opponent. We used the price of the good (i.e., the bicycle) as the only bargaining issue to facilitate the explanation of the network development process. In another paper, we introduced a second issue — i.e., the quality of the

good — to demonstrate the ability of the model to address a more life-like negotiation (Bui and Strand, 1992). The idea was that if a two-issue problem could be build, a n-issue problem could also be implemented.

As a final remark, the neural network proposed in this paper exhibits a behavior very similar to that of an expert system. The major difference between the neural networks and an expert system lies in the way information is represented. Facts and knowledge can be represented by rules in an expert system. They are represented by nodes and connections in a neural network. The process of evaluating why a decision is made can be done in an expert system by having it reveal which rules were invoked during the consultation. In the neural network, each node carries its meaning explicitly; a method of reasoning can be readily seen by observing which nodes are active.

The findings here suggest that continued research in neural networks to model the thought processes of negotiators holds great promise. The value of being able to model true beliefs and evaluation methods has an advantage over models which dictate what should be evaluated. This advantage is the opportunity to incorporate irrationalities into a model, and an ability to see how that irrationality affects the decision making process.

The neural network approach to solving a negotiation problem requires a different method of representing information than other approaches. In a complex problem representation, the network offers to the user relative ease of recognition of the relations inherent within a problem. However, the builder of the network faces a significant challenge. He must have an in-depth understanding of all of the elements involved in a problem and their interrelations. Learning paradigms should be explored to help the builder start with a comprehensive negotiation model and let the system learn and adjust itself to new negotiation situations. It is expected that such a learning paradigm would greatly enhance the development speed.

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